

BRIDGING THE GAP: EXPLORING THE MISMATCH BETWEEN INDUSTRIAL ARTS STRAND AND RELATED HIGHER EDUCATION COURSES

Ryan S. Cutamora ¹, Jan Nicole T. Napolis ², Raffy C. Sarmiento ²

¹ Science Department, Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School, City of Carmona, Cavite, Philippines

² Mathematics Department, Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School, City of Carmona, Cavite, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17960699>

ABSTRACT

This study examines the prevalence and underlying factors of strand–course mismatch among Industrial Arts (IA) graduates of Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School for School Year 2023–2024. Utilizing a descriptive quantitative research design and total enumeration sampling, data were gathered from 110 IA graduates to determine their chosen curriculum exits, the alignment of their higher education programs with their Senior High School (SHS) strand, and the reasons influencing their post-secondary decisions. Findings reveal that while 40% of graduates pursued higher education, a larger proportion (50.91%) immediately entered employment, and 9.09% opted for mid-level skills development. Among those who enrolled in college, 75% chose programs aligned with their Industrial Arts strand, whereas 25% pursued non-aligned courses. Analysis of decision-making factors shows that job opportunities significantly influenced students' choices, followed by personal interest and family support. Although personality traits were acknowledged as relevant, students did not strongly perceive their attributes as ideal for their chosen degrees. Responses also suggest that external experiences had minimal impact on course selection. The study highlights the essential role of the school's career guidance program in informing and supporting students' academic pathways, though further improvement is needed to ensure more consistent alignment between SHS specialization and higher education tracks. Strengthening career guidance, enhancing industry-school collaboration, and reinforcing student exposure to strand-related career opportunities are recommended to minimize mismatches. Overall, the research underscores the need for targeted interventions to support IA graduates in making

informed, career-aligned educational decisions, ultimately improving their academic success and long-term employability.

Keywords: *mismatch, career guidance, college program, college course, industrial arts, curriculum exit, higher education*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a human right, a powerful driver of development, and one of the strongest instruments for reducing poverty and improving health, gender equality, peace, and stability (The World Bank, n.d.). It cultivates and informs an individual's perspectives on many issues, helping them to interpret the world around them, build opinions, and enable the formation of their particular viewpoints (Geneva College, 2020).

However, education, specifically secondary education, sometimes has inherent issues when it comes to the transition to higher education. One prevalent issue that occurs among students beginning their career path is course mismatch. According to Quintos et al. (2020), course mismatch occurs when students choose a higher education course based on their career goal, which does not align with the current strand specialization that they belong to. This issue could have significant effects on the students' career goals as it would affect various factors such as motivation and competencies towards their selected courses.

Senior high school programs under secondary education are intended to prepare students before entering college, equipping them with the global skills, competencies, and knowledge needed to achieve successful career paths in the future. The different tracks, strands, and specializations are intended to determine which paths fit the students' strengths, passions, and skills. Moreover, it expands the learners' knowledge and skills, while at the same time, exposing them to their chosen field of study in preparation for college (Mapúa Malayan Colleges Mindanao, n.d.). In addition, knowing the student's aptitude, an inborn ability or gifting in specific aspects of education or work, and comprehending how they influence an individual's professional capabilities enables them to identify a career that best suits their unique strengths (Lynch, 2022). Course mismatches potentially restrict these advantages, wherein competency developed in the student's selected strand would be significantly underutilized and underprepared for the courses they selected.

According to Sotto (2020), the Industrial Arts strand plays an important role in our modern society; this strand wants to give background information and skills that they can acquire in industrial society. It offers different specializations like masonry, plumbing, carpentry, shielded metal arc welding, automotive servicing, driving, electrical installation, electronics repair, tile setting, metal works, pottery, furniture making, and motorcycle/minor engine servicing. Industrial Arts can offer a lot of career opportunities that they can use to become better people in this society.

However, students under the TVL track may experience major challenges in higher education. Based on a Quintos et al. (2020) study, the lowest strand alignment for college course enrollment is the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood track.

Despite several studies on strand-course mismatch, there is limited research specifically focusing on Industrial Arts graduates, particularly within the context of Cavite-based public senior high schools such as Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School. This creates a clear research gap regarding the factors influencing IA graduates' decisions and the extent to which mismatch occurs in this specific setting.

There are evident issues of higher education mismatch among students aiming to enroll in college courses but there is little data regarding the phenomenological reasoning on why such cases occur. This lack of localized and strand-specific data further strengthens the need to investigate the mismatch experienced by IA graduates. This study will aim to identify the rate of these issues occurring and the reasons why such phenomenon manifests.

Given these conditions, establishing updated and evidence-based insights becomes timely and essential, especially as SHS programs continue to evolve and career guidance efforts intensify nationwide. This study could ameliorate issues of possible course mismatch of upcoming graduates from Senior High School, specifically, the students of the Industrial Arts program by supplying the necessary justifications, providing relevant information, elucidating the frequency and mechanisms behind this issue, how such problem transpires and proposing the necessary interventions regarding course mismatch. This investigation intends to benefit future undergraduates by assisting them in selecting their aptitude for higher education courses and avoiding potential course and, ultimately, career mismatch.

Literature Review

It is crucial to align career paths for senior high school graduates to ensure their long-term success, satisfaction, and well-being. When graduates follow careers that correspond with their skills, interests, and aspirations, they are more inclined to excel professionally, enjoy greater job satisfaction, and make a positive contribution to the workforce. This alignment also yields societal benefits, nurturing a productive and resilient workforce that fuels economic growth and stability.

In the Industrial Arts Strand context, challenges often arise due to mismatches between students' natural inclinations and higher education or career choices. John Holland's Career Theory (1959) underscores the importance of aligning an individual's personality type—categorized under the RIASEC model—with compatible work environments. Students in the Industrial Arts Strand typically exhibit "Realistic" traits and thrive in hands-on, technical, and practical fields. However, misalignment occurs when students are directed toward academic paths that do not reflect their natural skills or interests, leading to diminished motivation and potential career dissatisfaction.

Mark Savickas's Career Construction Theory (2005) further emphasizes the importance of career adaptability. In this theory, students actively craft their career narratives by reflecting on their values, skills, and goals. This adaptability involves planning, controlling decisions, exploring career options, and building confidence.

Similarly, the Social Cognitive Career Theory (SCCT) by Lent, Brown, and Hackett (1994) highlights the role of self-efficacy, outcome expectations, and personal goals in career development. Many Industrial Arts students may lack confidence in pursuing higher education due to perceived challenges or limited exposure to opportunities.

Related Studies

Moving from the Industrial Arts strand in Senior High School (SHS) to higher education can be challenging, especially when students choose college programs that don't match their SHS specialization. This disparity, known as a "strand-course mismatch," may hinder academic success and career advancement.

Based on the study of Caballes (2022), Senior High school graduates from school years 2017-2018 and 2018-2019 found mismatch rates of 39% and 31%, respectively. The primary reasons for this misalignment included family pressure, accessibility of programs at nearby universities, and peer influence. The study emphasized the importance of intensified career guidance programs to bridge this gap and ensure students make informed decisions about their educational and career paths.

Similarly, Aguba and Villacruel (2023) emphasized aligning SHS strands with tertiary programs. The study suggests that educational institutions should establish bridging programs to ensure students are adequately prepared for their chosen higher education courses, thereby reducing the incidence of strand-course mismatches.

Also, according to the study of Baguio (2024), their findings suggest that SHS-TVL graduates are exploring various career paths that are not limited to degree programs directly related to their SHS strands. This highlights the importance of providing comprehensive career guidance and exposure to different fields to help students make informed decisions about their future education and career paths. The data also indicates that there is some alignment between SHS-TVL strands and the chosen degree programs, but there may be room for improvement in terms of strengthening this alignment to ensure that students are well-prepared for their chosen fields of study.

Similarly, with a study of Nazareno et al., 2021 found that the perceived alignment between SHS tracks and future career or higher-education opportunities significantly influenced students' track and career choices, highlighting the importance of providing comprehensive career guidance and support to help students make informed decisions about their educational and professional paths.

In the context of Kalinga, the Schools Division Office (SDO) has recognized the critical role of career guidance in addressing job-skill mismatches and reducing course

shifting among learners. The SDO-Kalinga has implemented division-wide career guidance advocacy programs aimed at helping students choose careers that align with their interests and skills, thereby enhancing their global competitiveness.

Kalinga National High School also launched a Career Guidance Advocacy Program for the 2024-2025 school year, targeting Grade 9 learners. This initiative underscores the school's commitment to early intervention in career planning, ensuring that students are well-prepared to select SHS strands and subsequent college courses that align with their career aspirations.

These initiatives highlight the importance of comprehensive career guidance programs bridging the gap between SHS specializations, such as the Industrial Arts strand, and higher education courses. By providing students with the necessary tools and information, educational institutions can reduce the incidence of strand-course mismatches and promote more effective transitions into higher education and the workforce.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the possibilities of a mismatch between the Industrial Arts strand and the courses enrolled in higher education institutions by students who graduated from Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School in School Year 2023–2024.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the rate of Industrial Arts graduates from Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School last School Year 2023-2024 who took the following curriculum exits:
 - a. higher education;
 - b. mid-level skills development;
 - c. entrepreneurship; and
 - d. employment?
2. What percentage of graduates enrolled in higher education courses that were aligned and not with the Industrial Arts strand in ALLSHS?
3. What factors affect Industrial Arts graduates' decision to choose higher education courses? Are there reasons for possible mismatch?
4. How career guidance program in Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School helps to reaffirm the preferred courses in college of Industrial Arts graduates to prevent possible mismatch?

METHODOLOGY

A. Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in a public senior high school in City of Carmona, Cavite, where the Industrial Arts strand under the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) track is

offered. The institution served as the setting for data collection, as it housed the graduates who were identified as the study's respondents.

B. Sampling

This study employed total enumeration sampling by surveying 110 participants out of 149 Industrial Arts graduates composed of Electrical Installation and Maintenance and Shielded Metals Arc Welding majors from School Year 2023–2024. Response rate was obtained by deducting untraceable respondents from the total number of IA graduates who served as target participants in this study.

C. Data Collection

The following steps are followed in data gathering to complete the proposed study:

Before arranging the steps, researchers drafted a letter requesting permission from their Public School District Supervisor and School Head, which served as evidence of authorization to carry out the legal procedure. The researchers asked the school registrar to provide data regarding the number of graduates from the previous school year. Then, they sought the assistance of the former class advisers, with whom they distributed consent forms and administered questionnaires via an online platform like Google Forms.

Before the survey, the researchers also explained the purpose of the study to the target respondents. Informed consent was provided for respondents whose ages are 18 years old or above. Their willingness to participate in the study has been sought. Data privacy has been emphasized in the data-gathering process. Upon the respondents' consent, the nature of the study was explained before the distribution of questionnaires.

The researchers adapted and modified the research instrument from the study of Baguio (2024). It also undertook validity and reliability tests under the careful examination of a registered psychometrician. After that, pilot testing and re-testing to refine the research instrument were done.

D. Research Instrument

To gather data, the researchers used a structured questionnaire adapted and modified from Baguio (2024). The instrument consisted of four sections:

1. Demographic Profile
2. Curriculum Exit After SHS
3. Course Alignment Information
4. Factors Influencing Course Choice

Section 4 consisted of 16 items measured using a 4-point Likert scale:

- 4 – Strongly Agree
- 3 – Agree

- 2 – Disagree
- 1 – Strongly Disagree

The questionnaire underwent content validation, reliability checking, and pilot testing to ensure clarity, consistency, and appropriateness.

E. Data Analysis

To interpret the gathered data, the study used the following statistical tools:

- *Frequency and Percentage* – to identify the curriculum exits of IA graduates.
- *Weighted Mean* – to determine the factors influencing students' decisions and possible reasons for course mismatch.
- *Descriptive analysis* – to summarize and present the alignment and non-alignment of chosen higher education programs with the IA strand.

These statistical treatments enabled the researchers to summarize the quantitative data meaningfully and align them with the study objectives.

F. Scope and Limitations

The study included IA graduates from School Year 2023–2024. It specifically focused on identifying curriculum exits, course alignment, and factors affecting course choice after graduation. However, untraceable respondents and alumni who did not pursue higher education were excluded from certain analyses, as they did not meet the necessary criteria for determining strand–course alignment. The study relied on self-reported data, which may be subject to respondent accuracy and honesty.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings of the study on the post-graduation pathways of Industrial Arts (IA) graduates from Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School for the school year 2023–2024. The results are organized according to the study's subproblems, focusing on the graduates' post-secondary outcomes, alignment of higher education courses with the IA strand, factors influencing course selection, and the role of the career guidance program in supporting informed decision-making. The data provide a detailed overview of graduation rates, curriculum exits, and the reasons behind course choices, as well as insights into how guidance programs help prevent possible mismatches between senior high school strands and college programs.

Research Question 1. What is the rate of Industrial Arts graduates from Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School last School Year 2023-2024 who took the curriculum exits in terms of higher education, mid-level skills development, entrepreneurship, and employment?

Table 1. Graduation Rate and Post-Graduation Pathways of IA Strand Graduates at Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School, SY 2023-2024

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
Target Respondents (Response Rate)	110	73.83%
Untraceable Respondents	39	26.17%
Total ABM Graduates (Graduation Rate)	149	100.00 %

This table helps to show how many graduates were part of the study and gives a clear picture of the level of participation and engagement in the post-graduation pathways analysis.

Research Question 2. What percentage of graduates enrolled in higher education courses that were aligned and not with the Industrial Arts strand in ALLSHS?

Table 2. Curriculum exits of Industrial Arts graduates from Angelo L. Loyola Senior Highschool During School Year 2023 – 2024

Curriculum Exits	Frequency	Rate
Higher Education	44	40.00%
Mid–Level Skills Development.	10	9.09%
Entrepreneurship	0	0
Employment	56	50.91%

Note: Table 2 shows that more Industrial Students choose to work after they graduate from Senior high school, with a frequency of 56 and a rate of 50.91%.

Table 3. Rate of Industrial Arts graduates in school year 2023 – 2024 that enrolled in colleges/universities

Curriculum Exits	Frequency	Rate
Aligned	33	75.00%
Not Aligned	11	25.00%

Table 3 shows the rate of students enrolled in universities/colleges, and their courses are categorized as aligned or not aligned. The aligned rate is 75%, and the not aligned or mismatch rate is 25.00%.

Research Question 3. What factors affect Industrial Arts graduates' decision to choose higher education courses? Are there reasons for possible mismatch?

Table 4. Rate of possible reasons for not taking a course in line with the Industrial Arts strand enrolled in Senior High School

Possible Reasons	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Personality		
1. My personality fits best in my chosen degree program that I take	2.91	Agree
2. My traits and understanding of the degree will give me an advantage on landing to my pursued career.	2.18	Agree
3. I am more productive in the career that I will practice due to my traits.	1.73	Disagree
4. My attributes should be ideal for the degree program that I would focus on.	1.73	Disagree
Family and Relatives		
1. My parents and/or relatives took the same degree program that I would pursue.	1.82	Disagree
2. Preferences are made by a relative since they will provide for the expenses.	1.73	Disagree
3. My family will give me support on the chosen degree program for me.	3.27	Agree
4. I believe that they are the one who are responsible to choose a degree program for me since they may know what is best for me.	3.36	Agree

Interest		
1. I am particularly interested in this degree program that I will pursue	2.64	Agree
2. I like doing things related to the degree program that I am specializing.	3.64	Agree
3. An experience stimulated my interest for this degree program.	1.91	Disagree
4. I see myself as competent at this degree program that I am pursuing or that I have pursued.	2.82	Agree
Job Opportunities		
1. There are abundant opportunities I can avail from the degree program I am pursuing.	3.82	Agree
2. The degree program that I chose will help me to find a suitable career easily.	3.82	Agree
3. The degree program that I would pursue is timely in-demand.	3.64	Agree
5. I am fully aware of the opportunities that surround	3.64	Agree
6. the degree program that I chose.		

Note: Table 4 shows the weighted mean of possible reasons for not taking college courses related to the Industrial Arts strand in senior high school. The highest possible reason is Job Opportunity.

Research Question 4. How career guidance program in Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School helps to reaffirm the preferred courses in college of Industrial Arts graduates to prevent possible mismatch?

To address the qualitative question regarding how the career guidance program in Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School helps reaffirm the preferred college courses of Industrial Arts graduates and prevent potential mismatch, we can organize the data into themes and codes using thematic analysis. Here are potential themes and codes based on the question:

Theme 1: Awareness and Understanding of Career Options

Code 1.1: Information about college programs

Code 1.2: Clarity on career paths related to Industrial Arts

Code 1.3: Knowledge about course prerequisites and requirements

Code 1.4: Exposure to a variety of career options beyond Industrial Arts

Theme 2: Alignment Between Senior High School Courses and College Programs

Code 2.1: Compatibility of senior high school curriculum with college courses

Code 2.2: Identification of gaps in preparation for higher education

Code 2.3: Transition support to bridge senior high and college education

Code 2.4: Reaffirmation of career goals and suitability of college courses

Theme 3: Guidance and Counseling Support

Code 3.1: One-on-one counseling sessions

Code 3.2: Group career guidance activities (workshops, seminars)

Code 3.3: Personalized career advice based on individual strengths and preferences

Code 3.4: Support for decision-making in choosing college courses

Theme 4: Student Confidence and Decision-Making

Code 4.1: Increased confidence in college course choice

Code 4.2: Reduced uncertainty about future career

Code 4.3: Validation of preferred course choices

Code 4.4: Empowerment to make informed decisions

Theme 5: Program Impact and Effectiveness

Code 5.1: Success stories of students who made better choices

Code 5.2: Perceived usefulness of career guidance sessions

Code 5.3: Feedback on the career guidance process

Code 5.4: Areas for improvement in the guidance program

Theme 6: Preventing Mismatch Between Strand and College Course

Code 6.1: Preventing students from choosing ill-fitting college courses

Code 6.2: Strategies for ensuring a good match between skills and future programs

Code 6.3: Tailored guidance to match industrial arts skills with appropriate courses

Code 6.4: Counseling intervention to avoid course mismatch

DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: Graduation Rate and Post-Graduation Pathways

Several studies have highlighted the challenges of tracking graduates after they leave senior high school (or equivalent), especially when institutions lack updated alumni contact information or resources for systematic follow-up. For example, American Institutes for Research (AIR) notes that “surveys of former participants of education programs ... often are unreliable as well as difficult and costly to execute” because of difficulties reaching alumni after graduation.

Similarly, Indiana University researchers Amber D. Lambert & Angie L. Miller (2014) showed that many graduate-tracer or alumni surveys suffer from low response rates due to outdated contact information, alumni mobility, and lack of alumni engagement — often far below 50 %.

Research Question 2: Post-Graduation Curriculum Exits

The results indicate that 50.91% of graduates opted for employment, while 40.00% pursued higher education, and none chose entrepreneurship. This suggests that IA graduates primarily view the strand as a pathway to immediate workforce participation or

further studies, rather than as preparation for business ventures. The absence of entrepreneurship aligns with evidence from secondary and vocational-level education contexts. For example, “What young entrepreneurs learned in secondary school...and didn’t” (2023) shows that many entrepreneurs recalled their secondary schooling did not include explicit entrepreneurship coursework or business-oriented training, leaving them with limited entrepreneurial readiness. Similarly, Caliat, Dalhadi, and Ishmael (2024) found that although senior high school students may express interest in business, actual entrepreneurial intention or start-up activity is often hindered by lack of practical exposure, capital, and business-experience opportunities. Together, these studies suggest that without a deliberate, well-implemented entrepreneurship curriculum, industrial arts or vocational strands may not foster business-oriented skills or entrepreneurial orientation among graduates.

Research Question 3: Factors Affecting Higher Education Course Choice

Analysis of Table 4 revealed that job opportunities were the most influential factor guiding course selection, with weighted means ranging from 3.64 to 3.82. Students agreed that their personality, family support, and personal interest also played significant roles in decision-making, while external experiences and alignment of personal traits with the chosen degree were less influential.

These findings suggest that IA graduates prioritize career prospects and employability when choosing college programs, consistent with the human capital theory, which posits that students make educational choices based on potential economic returns (Becker, 1993). Family support was significant but not controlling, indicating that students exercise autonomy in their decisions while valuing guidance.

Research Question 4: Career Guidance Program Effectiveness

The thematic analysis highlighted six key themes reflecting the effectiveness of the career guidance program. Graduates reported that the program increased awareness of career options, clarified alignment between SHS and college courses, and provided personalized counseling that enhanced decision-making confidence. The program also contributed to preventing mismatches, helping students select college courses suitable for their IA skills and interests.

These findings support previous studies emphasizing the importance of structured career guidance in senior high school to facilitate informed transitions to higher education and employment. Specifically, the program’s ability to improve student confidence and validate course choices aligns with Quintos, Caballes, Gapad, and Valdez (2020), who reported that intensified career guidance reduces mismatch between SHS strands and college programs, helping students make more informed educational and career decisions.

Conclusions

The study provides valuable insights into the post-graduation pathways and factors influencing the decision-making process of Industrial Arts (IA) graduates at Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School (ALLSHS) during the 2023-2024 academic year. The findings reveal that while most IA graduates choose either employment (50.91%) or higher education (40%), a significant portion (25%) of those who pursued higher education enrolled in courses that were not aligned with the IA strand. This mismatch may reflect the influence of various personal, familial, and situational factors.

The study identified key factors that affect students' course choices, including their personality traits, family support, personal interest, and job opportunities. Most students agreed that job prospects played a major role in their decision-making, with many believing their chosen degree programs offered good career opportunities. Additionally, students expressed interest in their chosen fields but did not necessarily feel their traits perfectly aligned with the degree programs they pursued. Family support also played a key role, with many students feeling that their families influenced their decision-making process, but they did not believe their families were making the decisions for them.

Career guidance programs at ALLSHS appear to play a critical role in helping students choose college programs, providing valuable information about career options and offering counseling support. These programs seem effective in preventing potential mismatches between the IA strand and students' chosen courses, particularly by helping students identify suitable career paths and reaffirm their college course decisions. However, there is room for improvement in ensuring that students make fully informed decisions that align with their skills and interests, potentially through more tailored counseling and additional exposure to diverse career options.

In conclusion, while the career guidance program helps prevent course mismatches to some extent, there remains a need for more targeted interventions that bridge the gap between students' IA background and their higher education choices. This will better ensure that students select degree programs that complement their Senior High School track and prepare them for a successful future in their chosen careers.

Recommendations

The researchers give some recommendations for the schools to enhance career guidance and lessen the mismatch of courses in the strand taken by the students.

1. *Enhance Career Guidance and Counseling*

The significant proportion (50.91%) of Industrial Arts students choosing employment over further education indicates a possible gap between the curriculum and industry demands or opportunities. Enhancing career counseling services may assist students in comprehending the available career paths and options, motivating them to seek higher education that aligns with their aspirations and long-term objectives.

2. *Enhance coordination between educational programs and industry requirements.*
As many students opt for courses unrelated to their streams to pursue better job prospects, closer collaboration between educational institutions and industries is essential. Schools and universities should partner with businesses to ensure that the skills they teach align with current job market demands. Such collaboration can help bridge the gap between education and employment opportunities, motivating students to remain in their chosen fields of study.
3. *Highlight Education's Importance for Career Growth*
A notable 25% of students are taking courses that do not match their strand, indicating potential misconceptions about the actual value of education. Programs focused on the long-term advantages of higher education, such as increased earning potential and career growth, could motivate students to select courses that more closely align with their original strand and ambitions.
4. *Targeted Support for Advancing Mid-Level Skills*
With 9.09% of students concentrating on developing mid-level skills, especially those in TESDA programs, it is crucial to keep offering avenues for additional upskilling and certifications. These programs should receive increased promotion, and students ought to be informed about the complete array of certifications and training to enhance career prospects, fostering a balance between skilled employment and higher education goals.
5. *Changing the process of Collecting Data*
Since the study used Google Forms to collect the data, the researchers recommend using interviews or focus group discussions as these are some of the most effective ways to collect data.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Addressing a range of ethical considerations to protect participants' safety, rights, and well-being was fundamental in the conduct of the research. Researchers were required to obtain proper authorization to carry out the study, which sought to answer specific research questions while upholding participants' autonomy. Central to these ethical responsibilities was the acquisition of voluntary and informed consent. Researchers needed to ensure that parents or guardians clearly understood the study's purpose, procedures, and overall nature prior to granting their consent.

In addition, minor participants were required to provide informed assent, indicating that they comprehended the study and willingly agreed to take part. The maintenance of confidentiality and anonymity was also imperative. Participants' personal information had to be kept private, and no identifying details were to be disclosed without explicit permission. Furthermore, researchers were obliged to communicate any potential risks—whether physical, emotional, or psychological—and to implement appropriate measures to minimize these risks. By rigorously addressing these ethical considerations, the

researchers upheld the integrity of the study while safeguarding the rights and welfare of all participants.

Acknowledgments

The researchers would like to convey their sincerest gratitude to the following persons who contributed a lot to the completion of this study:

First, Almighty God, thanks for giving the researcher the strength and courage to accomplish the study successfully, for guiding them through every challenge, and for providing the wisdom to persevere.

Second, the researchers would like to express their deep gratitude to Congressman Roy M. Loyola of District V of Cavite Province and City Mayor Dahlia A. Loyola of Carmona City, Cavite, for their steadfast support in making this study possible. Their encouragement, commitment, and resources have been invaluable throughout the research process, and their contributions have played a crucial role in ensuring the success of this project.

Third, the researchers would also like to sincerely thank Dr. Elsa O. De Leon, Public Schools District Supervisor, and Mrs. Laarni S. Doliente, Principal II of Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School, for permitting the study at their esteemed institution. The researcher appreciates their consistent support and the opportunity to collaborate with them, which played a significant role in ensuring the study's success. Their commitment to fostering educational research is highly commendable.

In addition, the researchers would like to thank the Faculty and Staff, especially those from the Faculty of Technical-Vocational-Livelihood, for allowing them to gather data from their department. The researchers appreciated the resources and time given. Lastly, the researchers want to extend thanks to the alumni from Technical-Vocational-Livelihood under Industrial Arts Strand, specializing in Electronics and Installation Maintenance from Angelo L. Loyola Senior High School batch 2023-2024, for their valuable time, patience, and involvement in the study.

REFERENCES

- Aguba, M. I., & Villacruel, P. D. (2023). Senior High School strand alignment and its implication to the tertiary programs: A basis for bridging program. *The Research Probe*, 3(2), 22–27. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.53378/trp.12232>
- American Institutes for Research. (2020). *Following Students After Graduation: Best practices for tracking postsecondary and workforce outcomes*. AIR.
- Baguio, M., Bas, M., Bucar, J., Bongato, G. P., & Rollorata, P. (2024). Alignment of Senior High School TVL strand to degree programs enrolled. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 25(10), 1318–1331. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13862134>
- Becker, G. S. (1993). *Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education* (3rd ed.). University of Chicago Press.
- Caliat, C. J., Dalhadi, N. J., & Ishmael, K. M. (2024). Entrepreneurship education in the lens of the senior high school students. *ASEAN Journal on Science and Technology for Development*, 41(1). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.61931/2224-9028.1554>

- Geneva College. (2020, September 18). Embracing Educational Benefits: Why is Education Important? Geneva College. Retrieved from <https://www.geneva.edu/blog/higher-education/why-is-education-important>
- Holland, J. L. (1959). *A theory of vocational choice*. Evanston, IL: Northwestern University Press.
- Lambert, A. D., & Miller, A. L. (2014). Lower response rates on alumni surveys might not mean lower response representativeness. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 37(1), 5-23.
- Lent, R. W., Brown, S. D., & Hackett, G. (1994). Toward a unifying social cognitive theory of career and academic interest, choice, and performance. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 45(1), 79–122.
- Lynch, M. (2022, April 18). Teacher-Centered Philosophies: Everything You Need to Know. *The Advocate*. <https://www.theadvocate.org/aptitude-everything-you-need-to-know/>
- Mapúa Malayan College Mindanao. (n.d.). Importance of Choosing the Right Senior High School Track or Strands. Mapúa Malayan College Mindanao. <https://mcm.edu.ph/the-importance-of-choosing-the-right-senior-high-school-track-or-strands/>
- Nazareno, A., Roxas-Villanueva, R. M., & colleagues. (2021). Factors associated with career track choice of Senior High School students. *Philippine Journal of Science*, 150(5), 1043–1060.
- Quintos, C. A., Caballes, D. G., Gapad, E. M., & Valdez, M. R. (2020). Exploring between SHS strand and college course mismatch: Bridging the gap through school policy on intensified career guidance program. *CiiT International Journal of Data Mining and Knowledge Engineering*, 12(10–12), 153–162. Retrieved from <https://www.i-scholar.in/index.php/CiiTDMKE/article/view/207480>
- Quintos, C., & Caballes, D. G. (2022). Exploring Between SHS Strand and College Course Mismatch: Bridging the Gap Through School Policy on Intensified Career Guidance Program. *CiiT International Journal of Data Mining and Knowledge Engineering*, 12(10–12), 156–161
- Savickas, M. L. (2005). The theory and practice of career construction. In S. D. Brown & R. W. Lent (Eds.), *Career development and counseling: Putting theory and research to work* (pp. 42–70). John Wiley & Sons.
- Sotto, Y. (2020, February 11). Industrial Arts Strand. *Press Reader*. Retrieved from <https://www.pressreader.com/philippines/sunstarpampanga/20200211/2816768>
- The World Bank. (n.d.). Education Overview: Development News, Research, Data. The World Bank. Retrieved from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/education/overview>